

EVALUATION OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL ECONOMICS CURRICULUM IN OYO STATE NIGERIA

Professor Elizabeth Adenike EMEKE

Institute of Education, University of Ibadan, Nigeria. Email: emeke2002@yahoo.com, 08054459158 or 08023294917

Dr. Amusa Ayodele AJIBADE

*Teaching Service Commission (TESCOM), Oyo Zonal Office Oyo State Nigeria. Email: ajibadeamusa2013@gmail.com
08055342075 or 08165044554*

Corresponding author: *Dr. Amusa Ayodele AJIBADE
Tel.: +08055342075 Email: *ajibadeamusa2013@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The study evaluated the implementation of secondary school Economics curriculum in Oyo State along all the four objectives, and on the basis of five implementation variables (students' study skills, teachers' attitude, resource utilisation, teachers' evaluation methods and resource availability). Survey design using the Input, Process and Outcome Evaluation Model guided the study. The secondary schools in Oyo State were clustered along the eight educational zones. Three teachers and 20 students were randomly selected from each of the 10% of the schools selected in each zone. Five instruments: School Materials Inventory ($r=0.84$), Economics Achievement Test ($r=0.78$), Economics Students ($r=0.76$), Economics Teachers ($r=0.74$), Economics Students' Perception of Teachers' Resource Utilization and Attitude ($r=0.71$) Questionnaires were used for data collection. Data collected were analysed using frequency counts and multiple regression at 0.05 alpha level. Students' performance in Economics was average (74.4%). Their perceived skills in prudence in resource management (1.2%); finding solution to problems (2.1%) and appreciation of economic, cultural and social values (10.6%) were low. Only resource utilisation had significant relative contribution to Economics curriculum implementation ($\beta = 0.17$). Students' perception of the teachers' attitude ($B=0.14$) and students' study skills ($B=0.19$) contributed positively to dignity of labour. There were more male teachers than females (52.8%). Material resources available in school were well utilised but they were not adequate with over 80% inadequacy level. The implementation of secondary school Economics curriculum had been poor in Oyo State there is the need for adequate provision of human and material resources. Students should be encouraged to develop positive study skills, while teachers should teach skills along with evaluation.

KEYWORDS

Secondary, Implementation, Economics and Teacher.

INTRODUCTION

Curriculum, to a very large extent, determines the success or failure of any nation's educational development because, in its wider sense, it encompasses the whole of learners' experiences both formal and informal and to achieve its set goals, it has to be properly implemented because many good programmes suffer setbacks at the implementation stage and also it has to be constantly evaluated so as not to lose focus. Curriculum is all the planned experiences provided by the school to assist the learners in attaining the designated learning outcomes to the best of their abilities (Ayodele & Adegbile, 2007). It is an attempt to communicate the essential principles and features of an educational proposal in such a form that it is open to critical scrutiny and is capable of effective translation into practice (Altricher 2010).

Curriculum is not limited to the schools, learners and the teachers but also about the development of the society in general. To effectively implement the curriculum, resources in form of human, money and materials must not only be available but properly utilized. Adeogun & Ofisila (2008) categorized educational resources into four groups, that is, human, material, physical and financial resources. Human resources are the teaching staff, physical resources included libraries, classrooms and a host of others physical infrastructure while material resources include textbooks, charts and maps among others. The instructional materials according to Agbulu & Wever (2011) are important because they are used for the transfer of information from one individual to another, help teacher in extending his/her learners' horizon of experience, stimulate learners' interest and help both teachers and learners to overcome physical limitation during the presentation of subject matter among others.

A study carried out by Akinsanya (2010) to determine the differential distribution and utilization of human resources on students' performance in state owned and federal schools revealed that both materials and human resources were practically inadequate and where they were available, they were not well utilized in those two types of schools. The study also revealed that physical facilities like libraries which were inadequate affected students' performance. The correct use of these materials or educational resources, according to Usman (2016), are central to the educational process because they play an important role in the achievement of educational goals and objectives since they facilitate teachers' work and accelerate learning on the part of the students. This is also corroborated by Akinsanya (2010) who said that educational resources are important because the goal of any school depends on adequate supply and utilization of physical and material resources among others things, since those resources enhance proper teaching and learning.

Availability of resources, in the opinion of Asogwa, Onu & Egbo (2013) refer to the condition of being obtainable or accessible at a particular point in time. In this study, availability means the condition with which teachers have access and make use of functional instructional materials for effective teaching and learning to students in senior secondary schools. It refers to the quality, quantity functionality and disposability of such instructional materials to teachers at every point in time for effective utilization. Utilization, according to Ragbu (2009), is the primary method by which asset performance is measured and business determined. Utilization, in this context, refers to the rate or how often an instructional material in education is put into use or services by teachers of Economics in senior secondary schools. Utilization of instructional materials depends on their availability in the schools. These resources must be properly managed for effective utilization

because the success or otherwise of an educational system depends not only on the availability and utilization of resources but also on how these resources have been judiciously and prudently managed. Resource management, according to Olaleye (2014) and Adetoro (2009) is the effective and efficient deployment of any organization's resources to where they are needed. Management of resources is germane to the sustainable development of educational system.

Curriculum implementation involves a lot of inputs such as students, teachers, funds, instructional materials, classrooms and furniture. Effective interaction among these inputs will result in effective implementation. Success of curriculum implementation depends on the availability of resources especially teachers because teachers are the principal actors. Ahmed-Rufai (2012) states that, the poor performance of students in examinations recorded in recent years is attributable to poor quality of teachers. To effectively implement the curriculum, adequately trained and well-motivated teachers must be available. National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) (2006) indicated some of the functions of the Economics teacher in curriculum implementation as breaking down of the curriculum, selecting learning content, and objectives, evaluating and reporting student performance and acting as parents among other things.

Economics is an elective subject in the senior secondary school curriculum, but its civic and educational values make it to be chosen by many students. Economics according to Anyanwuocha (2004) is very useful to individuals and the society because it teaches how best to use the limited resources with minimum waste by providing a rational guide to individuals, firms and governments in the allocation of scarce resources. Khumalo (2012) perceives Economics as the study of how humans use knowledge to identify resources and use these scarce resources to create, using knowledge, and commodities and distribute them among people.

Economics was introduced late into the Nigeria school curriculum. The late introduction, according to Olaoye (2005) might not be unconnected with the views of some early educationists like Robbins (1955) and Piaget (1969) who perceived Economics as a subject for adults. But by the middle of the 1960's, people in Britain and Nigeria started accepting the educational and civic values of Economics. Since the introduction of Economics students' enrolment has been on the increase as reflected on Table 1.

Table 1: West African School Certificate Examination Entries in Economics for Oyo State Candidates (2004 -2016)

Year	Total Entry for All subjects	Total sat for Economics	% of Economics To Total Entry for all Subjects
2004	49562	46841	94.51%
2005	55341	54125	97.80%
2006	62942	58572	93.06%
2007	64232	59712	92.96%
2008	35952	34239	94.24%

2009	25577	24581	96.11%
2010	42509	40265	94.72%
2011	46971	45309	96.46%
2012	43357	42710	98.51%
2013	74165	72624	97.92%
2014	33673	31989	94.99%
2015	31721	29187	92.01%
2016	29068	27093	93.21%

Source: Planning, Research and Statistics Department, Ministry of Education Ibadan.

Table 1 shows that, over 90% of the total entry sat for Economics every year under review. This can be attributed to the subject being relatively easy to pass, containing only nine broad topics which can be covered and tested at lower levels of cognition.

Table 2: Oyo State Candidates WAEC-May/June Results in Economics (2004-2016)

Year	Total Sat	Total Credit Grades	% of Grades 1-6 to Total Sat	Pass Grades	% of Grades 7 & 8 to Total Sat	Fail Grade 9	% of Grade 9 to Total Sat
2004	46841	8432	18.01	14421	31.21	28888	50.11
2005	54125	8930	16.51	20676	38.22	25519	45.33
2006	58572	12839	21.92	19394	33.11	26339	44.97
2007	59712	13325	22.32	20220	33.86	26167	43.82
2008	34239	3727	10.89	12216	35.69	17939	52.41
2009	24581	3596	14.63	5608	22.81	14820	60.29
2010	40265	11956	27.80	13801	34.27	15197	37.74
2011	45309	10768	23.78	16724	36.93	17795	39.29
2012	42710	13691	32.04	3082	7.22	25937	34.78
2013	72624	30530	42.03	22310	30.71	19161	26.38
2014	31989	7280	22.76	7972	24.91	16446	51.42
2015	29187	5245	17.13	6834	22.21	17078	58.52

Source: Planning, Research and Statistics Department, Ministry of Education Ibadan

An examination of Table 2 showed that the performance of students was generally poor because with the exception of year 2013 where students had a little above 40% pass (which is also not a good performance), less than 33% pass was recorded in the remaining twelve years under review. These results indicated that more than 67% of the students had to repeat Economics every year if they intend to pursue any course that requires credit pass in the subject. This general poor performance of students in Economics needs to be addressed in order to improve the students' performance in Economics and at the same time sustains their interest in the subject. It is therefore necessary to look at the objectives of Economics at Senior Secondary School level and thus Economics curriculum is designed to achieve the following objectives:

- 1 To equip students with the basic principles of Economics necessary for useful living and for higher education.
- 2 To prepare and encourage students to be prudent and effective in the management of scarce resources.
- 3 To raise students' respect for the dignity of labour and their appreciation of economic, cultural and social values of our society and
- 4 To enable students acquire knowledge for the practical solution of the economic problems for the Nigerian society, other developing countries and the world at large

Evaluation plays prominent roles in curriculum implementation because the essence of curriculum in education is to bring about certain changes in the learners. Evaluation enables teachers to determine whether there are changes or not and the extent of the changes. Evaluation, according to Alkin (1970) is the process of ascertaining the decision to be made, selecting related information and collecting and analysing information in order to report summary data useful to decision makers in selecting among alternatives. In the words of Okpala & Onocha (1994), educational evaluation is a continuous process which underlies all good teaching and learning activities. There are two main forms of evaluation, formative evaluation and summative evaluation.

There are research works on achievement in Economics, For instance, Owolabi (1996) investigated student's attitude to instructional questioning, critical thinking ability, study habit and self concept on students' achievement in Economics. Adu (2002) looked at two problem-based learning strategies, quantitative ability and gender as determinants of student's academic achievement in Economics. Olaoye (2005) looked at teacher characteristics and students' attitudes as determinants of students' performance in Economics at the secondary school level in Oyo state. Reilly & Buchan (2010) carried out a study on students' academic performance by a sample of Economics candidates using two cohorts of students in England and Wales taking Economics examination. A research work on Economics curriculum that focused on the four stated objectives of Economics is necessary to discover where the problem of poor performance of Economics really lies. In view of the above, this research work evaluated the implementation of senior secondary school Economics curriculum in Oyo State drawn from the four stated objectives. Therefore, the following five evaluation objectives were taken into consideration in the course of this study.

Evaluation Objectives

The objectives of this study, therefore, are:

1. To establish the extent to which students have been equipped with basic principles of Economics necessary for useful living and for higher education.

2. To find out how students perceive their prudence and effectiveness are in the management of scarce resources
3. To establish the level of students' perception to the dignity of labour.
4. To determine the level of students' appreciation of economic, cultural and social values of our society.
5. To establish the extent to which students are knowledgeable about practical solutions to the economic problems of the Nigerian society

Statement of the Problem

The high rate at which students initially passed Economics in 1967, when it was just introduced in public examinations such as that of WAEC made it popular among Senior Secondary School students. It was considered to be very easy to pass, but in recent times, students' performance in Economics in public examinations generally, has not been as encouraging as it should be. Majority of the available research studies focused mainly on Economics achievement, but other areas of Economics objectives such as skills in resource management, solving economic problem, respect for dignity of labour and respect for cultural and social value of our society which knowledge of Economics is supposed to instill in students were left out. A research work that focused on the four Economics objectives is necessary. It is against this background that this study focused on the implementation of Economics curriculum based on the four stated Economics objectives, that is, problem of poor performance of students in Economics and the skills possessed by Economics students in resource management, solving Economics problems, respect for the dignity of labour and respect for cultural and social value of our society.

Research questions

- 1a. What is the level of Oyo State Students' achievement in Economics?
- 1b. What is the level of the students' perception of their prudence in resource management?
- 1c. What is the level of the students' perception of their ability to solve Economics problem?
- 1d: What is the level of the students' perception of their respect for dignity of labour?
- 1e. What is the level of the students' perception of their appreciation of economic, cultural and social values of the society?
2. What is the profile of Economics teachers in respect of their:
 - i. Gender, ii. Qualification and iii. Teaching Experience?
3. What is the level of availability and adequacy of school materials?
4. What is the level of resource utilization?
5. What is the pattern of evaluation methods?
6. What are the relative and composite contributions of Curriculum Implementation variables?
7. What are the relative and composite contributions of Curriculum Implementation variables?

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9. What are the relative and composite contributions of curriculum implementation variables?
10. What are the relative and composite contributions of Curriculum Implementation Variables?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design and Evaluation Model

This study adopted a survey research approach and Input, Process and Outcome Model (IPO model) introduced by Scriven and Stake (1967). The model was adopted because the focus of the study is on the implementation of curriculum and in a school system, the three components of Input, Process and Outcome are necessary.

Table 3: The Input, Process and Outcome Model (IPO MODEL)

Inputs	Processes	Outcomes
Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resource utilization • Implementation strategies • Teaching strategies • Monitoring and evaluation carried on Econs out of Head of Departments. 	Students' achievement in:
Human Resources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teachers' attitude to Econs. 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economics • Resource management skills • Solution to Economics problems skills • Respect for cultural and social value skills
Material Resources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Library books on Econs. • Journals on Econs • Teachers' Reference 		

Population and Sampling Technique

The target population for the study comprised all SS III Economics students. A multi-stage sampling technique was used in this study. In the first stage, population proportional to size was used to select 10% of number of schools in each of the existing eight educational zones and 30% of the number of teachers in each zone. In the second stage, 20 students per school were randomly selected from each of the participating schools to constitute the participants making a total of 820 students and 123 teachers.

Instrumentation

Five instruments: School Materials Inventory ($r = 0.84$), Economics Achievement Test ($r = 0.78$), Economics Students ($r = 0.76$), Economics Teachers ($r = 0.74$), Economics Students' Perception of Teachers' Resource Utilization and Attitude ($r = 0.71$) Questionnaires were used for data collection.

Method of Data Analysis

The data generated by the study were analysed using frequencies and percentages to answer research questions 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 while Multiple Regression was employed for research questions 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1a: What is the level of Oyo State Students' Achievement in Economics?

Table 4a: Frequency Distribution of Students' Performance in Economics

Categories	Range of achievement score	No of participants	Percentage
Low performance	0 -15	100	12.2%
Average performance	16 -23	610	74.4%
High performance	24 -40	110	13.4%

The result in Table 4 revealed the performance of students in Economics. One hundred students (100) 12.2% performed below average, six hundred and ten students (610) 74.4% recorded average performance and one hundred and ten students (110) 13.4% had high performance in Economics. Generally the performance of students was encouraging because 74.4% fell within the average performance group. However, on the whole, this did not reflect a very good performance,

Research Question 1b: What is the level of students' perception of their skills in prudence in resource management?

Table 4b: Level of students' perception of their prudence in resource management

Categories	Score Range	No of Participant	Percentage
Low	0 – 26	672	81.9 %
Average	27 - 53	138	16.8%
High	54 -80	10	1.2%

Table 4b show that the level of students' perception of their prudence in resource management. The Table reveals that 81.9% of the participants perceived low skills, 16.8% perceived average skills and 1.2% perceived high skills in their prudence in resource management. The implication of this is that, the level of students' perception of their prudence in resource management was generally low.

Research Question 1c: What is the level of students' skills in their ability to solve economic problem?

Table: 4.1c. Level of students' perception of their skills in their ability to solve economic problem

Categories	Score Range	No of Participant	Percentage
Low	0 – 30	710	86.6%
Average	31 - 61	93	11.3%
High	62 – 92	17	2.1%

Table 4c show the level of students' perception of their skills to solve economics problem. The Table reveals that 86.6% of the participants had low skills, 11.3% had average skills and 2.1% had high skills in their ability to solve economics problem. The implication of this is that the level of students' perception of their skills to solve economic problem was generally low.

Research Question 1d: What is the level of students' skills in their respect for dignity of labour?

Table: 4d: Level of students' perception of their respect for dignity of labour

Categories	Scores Range	No of Participant	Percentage
Low	0 – 15	643	78.4%
Average	16 - 23	132	16.1%
High	24 – 40	45	5.5%

Table 4d shows the level of students' perception of their respect for dignity of labour. The Table reveals that 78.4% of the participants had low skills in the level of their 'perception of their respect for dignity of labour, 16.1% and 5.5% had average and high perceptions respectively. The implication of this is that, the level of students' perception of their respect for dignity of labour was low.

Research Question 1e: What is the level of students' skills in their appreciation of economic, cultural and social values of the society?

Table: 4e: Level of students' perception of their appreciation of economic, cultural and social values of the society

Categories	Scores Range	No of Participant	Percentage
Low	0 – 26	604	73.7%
Average	27 - 53	129	15.7%
High	54 – 80	87	10.6%

Table 4e shows the level of students' perception of their appreciation of economic, cultural and social values of the society. The Table reveals that 73.7% of the participants had low level of perception to appreciate economic, cultural and social values of the society, 15.7% had average perception and 10.6% had high perception. The implication of this is that, level of students' perception to appreciate economic, cultural and social values of the society was generally low.

Research Question 2: What is the profile of Economics teachers with respect to their gender, qualification and teaching experience?

Table 5: Economics Teachers' Profiles

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Male	65	52.8
Female	58	47.2
Qualification		
NCE	19	15.4
First Degree	72	58.5
Master Degree	27	22.0
PhD	5	4.1
Teachers' Teaching experience		
Less than 5 Years	8	6.5
5-10 Years	25	20.3
11-15 Years	33	26.8
16-20 Years	39	31.7
Above 20 Years	18	14.6

The result as presented in Table 5 shows that while 52.8 percent of the sampled teachers were male, 47.2% were female. Table 5 also shows that 15.4% of the Economics teachers were NCE holders, 58.5% were bachelor degree holders and 22.0% and 4.1% held master and doctor of philosophy degrees respectively. Also Table 5 showed that while 6.5% of the teachers were very new in the profession with less than 5 years teaching experience 20.3% of the teachers had 5-10 years teaching experience as Economics teachers, 26.8% and 31.7% of the teachers had 11-15 and 16-20 years teaching experience as Economics teachers respectively while 31.7% had over 20years teaching experience as Economics teachers.

Research Question 3: What is the level of availability and adequacy of school material resources?

Table 6: Availability and Adequacy of School Material Resources

School Material Resources	School Materials Availability		School Materials Adequacy	
	Not Available	Available	Adequate	Not Adequate
Journals and Periodicals on Economics	89 (72.4%)	34 (27.6%)	1(2.9%)	33(97.1%)
Teachers' Reference Books on Economics	0	123(100.0%)	0	123(100.0%)
Teachers' Unit Plan on Economics	0	123(100.0%)	9(7.3%)	114(92.7%)
Scheme of works for Economics	0	123(100.0%)	9(7.3%)	114(92.7%)
Continuous Assessment Record Books for Economics	0	123(100.0%)	9(7.3%)	114(92.7%)
Marks Books for Economics	0	123(100.0%)	9(7.3%)	114(92.7%)
Diaries for Economics	0	123(100.0%)	0	123(100.0%)
Students' Attendance Register	0	123(100.0%)	17(13.8%)	106(86.2%)
Lesson Notes for Economics	0	123(100%)	0	123(100.0%)

Result as presented in Table 6 shows that all the sampled teachers indicated that the material resources needed for the teaching of Economics were available in the schools with an exception of “Journals and Periodicals on Economics” which were only available in the 27.6% of the sampled schools. One hundred percent (100%) of the teachers indicated that “Teachers' Reference Books on Economics” and “Lesson Notes for Economics” were not adequately made available for their use.

Research Question 4: What is the level of resource utilization in the schools?

Table 7: Teachers' level of Economics resource materials utilization in the schools

Teachers Sex	Teachers' Resource Utilization Level	
	Low Utilization	High Utilization
Male	4(6.2%)	61(93.8%)
Female	0	58(100.0%)
Teachers' Qualification		
NCE	0	19(100.0%)
First Degree	4(5.6%)	68(94.4%)

Master Degree	0	27(100.0%)
PhD	0	5(100.0%)
Total	4(3.3%)	119(96.7%)

The result as presented in Table 7 shows that teachers' level of utilization of available resources in the schools was encouraging. The result showed that while 93.8% and 100.0% of male and female teachers highly utilized the available resource materials, 100.0% of teachers with each of NCE, Master degree and PhD and 94.4% of teachers with first degree indicated that their level of resource materials utilization of the available materials was high. In general, the results as presented in Table 4.4 showed that while level of utilization of available resource materials of the teachers was low (3.3%), the level of utilization of available resource materials by 96.7% of the teachers was high.

Research Question 5.What is the pattern of evaluation methods?

Table 8: Teachers' Pattern of Evaluation Methods

Economics Evaluation Methods	Evaluation Methods Usage			
	Never used	Rarely used	Occasionally used	Frequently Used
Multiple Choice	0	4(3.3%)	115(93.5%)	4(3.3%)
Matching Item	2(1.6%)	119(96.7%)	2(1.6%)	0
Alternative Response Item	8(6.5%)	0	115(93.5%)	0
True or False Choice Item	0	117(95.1%)	4(3.3%)	2(1.6%)
Essay Type	0	2(1.6%)	4(3.3%)	117(95.1%)
Completion Item	6(4.9%)	2(1.6%)	115(93.5%)	0
Observation Method	123(100.0%)	0	0	0
Interviewing	121(98.4%)	0	0	2(1.6%)
Assignments	11(8.9%)	0	106(86.2%)	6(4.9%)
Using Rating Scales	123(100.0%)	0	0	0

The result as presented in Table 8 shows the pattern of teachers' evaluation methods for teaching and learning of Economics in the schools. It could be seen in the Table that 95.1% of teacher frequently used essay type while 93.5% of the teachers occasionally made use of multiple choice, alternative response item and completion item. Table 4.5 also shows that 96.7% and 95.1% of the teachers rarely made use of matching and true or false choice item. Furthermore, all the 123 sampled teachers used rating scale in their evaluation of students in the schools.

Research Question 6: What are the relative and composite contributions of curriculum implementation variables (Resource utilization, teachers’ attitude, students’ study skills and teachers’ evaluation method) to students’ achievement in Economics?

Table 9: Beta coefficient and t-ratio for relative composite contribution of curriculum implementation variables to students’ achievement in Economics

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
R = 0.171					
R ² = 0.029					
Adjusted R ² = 0.025					
F _(4, 822) = 6.201					
(Constant)	112.124	19.042		5.888	.000
Resource Utilization	2.769	.558	.172	4.960	.000
Students’ Perception of Teachers’ Attitude	.007	.038	.007	.193	.847
Students’ Perception of Teachers’ Evaluation Methods	.033	.050	.023	.658	.511
Economics Students’ Study Skills	.025	.067	.013	.367	.714

Table 9 shows that the sign of the coefficient of the independent variables (Resource utilization, teachers’ attitude, students’ study skills and teachers’ evaluation methods) were positive. This implies that students’ achievement in Economics increased with increase in each of the independent variables. Also, the probability ($p < .05$) as reported in Table 9 for resource utilization implies that the slope ($\beta = 2.769$) is statistically significant. However, teachers’ attitude, students’ study skills and teachers’ evaluation methods as reported in Table 9 implies that the slopes ($\beta = 0.007$, $\beta = .033$ and $\beta = 0.025$) respectively are statistically not significant. The intercept ($\beta = 112.124$, $p < .05$) as shown in the Table is also significant. Thus regression line $Y = 2.769X + 0.007 + 0.033X + 0.025X + 0.394$ means that when resource utilization increased by one unit (i.e. 1%), students’ achievement in Economics increased significantly by 276.9%, while a unit increase in teachers’ attitude, students’ study skills and teachers’ evaluation methods insignificantly increased students’ achievement in Economics by 0.7%, 3.3% and 2.5% respectively.

The result as presented in Table 9 also shows the model summary and overall fit statistics. The Table shows that adjusted R² of the model was 0.025 with R² = 0.029 that indicates that the combined contribution of the variables: Resource utilization, teachers’ attitude, students’ study skills and teachers’ evaluation method accounted for 2.9% of the variation in students’ achievement in Economics and with the F change value ($F_{(4, 822)} = 6.201$, $p < 0.05$) the combined contribution of the variables is significant.

Research Question 7: What are the relative and composite contributions of curriculum implementation variables (Resource utilization, teachers' attitude, students' study skills and teachers' evaluation method) to students' respect for dignity of labour skills?

Table 10: Beta coefficient and t-ratio for relative and composite contributions of curriculum implementation variables to students' respect for dignity of labour skills

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	27.514	7.998		3.440	.001
Resource Utilization	.042	.234	.006	.179	.858
Students' Perception of Teachers' Attitude	.066	.016	.141	4.125	.000
Students' Perception of Evaluation Methods	.003	.021	.005	.147	.883
Economics Students' Study Skills	.158	.028	.190	5.578	.000

Table 10 shows that the sign of the coefficient of the independent variables (Resource utilization, teachers' attitude, students' study skills and teachers' evaluation methods) were positive. This implies that students' achievement in Economics increased with increase in each of the independent variables. Also, the probability ($p < .05$) as reported in Table 10 for students' perception of teachers' attitude and Economics students' study skills implies that the slopes ($\beta = 0.066$ and $\beta = 0.158$) is statistically significant. However, resource utilization and students' perception of teachers' evaluation method implies with the slopes ($\beta = 0.042$ and $\beta = 0.003$) respectively are statically not significant. The intercept ($\beta = 27.514$, $p < .05$) as shown in the Table is also significant. Thus regression line $Y = 0.042X + 0.066X + 0.003X + 0.158X + 27.514$ means that when each of students perception of teachers' attitude and Economics students study skills increase by one unit (i.e. 1%), students' respect for dignity of labour skills increase significantly by 6.6% and 15.8% respectively while a unit increase in teachers' resource material utilization and teachers' evaluation method insignificantly increase students' respect for dignity of labour skills by 4.2%, and 0.3% respectively.

The result as presented in Table 10 also shows the model summary and overall fit statistics. The Table showed that adjusted R^2 of the model was 0.058 with $R^2 = 0.063$ indicating that the combined contributions of the variables: Resource utilization, teachers' attitude, students' study skills and teachers' evaluation method accounted for 6.3% of the variation in students' respect for dignity of labour skills and with the F change value ($F_{(4, 822)} = 13.767$, $p < 0.05$) the combined contribution of the variables is significant.

Research Question 8: What are the relative and composite contributions of curriculum implementation variables (Resource utilization, teachers' attitude, students' study skills and teachers' evaluation method) to students' respect for cultural and social values?

Table 11: Beta coefficient and t-ratio for relative and composite contribution of curriculum implementation variables to students' respect for cultural and social values

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	14.723	10.172		1.447	.148
Resource Utilization	.788	.298	.085	2.644	.008
Students' Perception of Teachers' Attitude	.024	.020	.039	-1.209	.227
Students' Perception of Evaluation Methods	.003	.027	.003	-.104	.917
Economics Students' Study Skills	.421	.036	.377	11.669	.000

Table 11 shows that the sign of the coefficient of the independent variables (Resource utilization, teachers' attitude, students' study skills and teachers' evaluation method) were positive. This implies that students' achievement in Economics increased with increase in each of the independent variables. Also, the probability ($p < .05$) as reported in Table 11 for resource materials utilization and Economics students study skills implies that the slopes ($\beta = 0.778$ and $\beta = 0.421$) is statistically significant.

However, students' perception of teachers' evaluation method and students' perception of teachers' attitude implies that the slopes ($\beta = 0.024$ and $\beta = 0.003$) respectively are statistically not significant. The intercept ($\beta = 14.723$, $p < .05$) as shown in the Table is also not significant. Thus regression line $Y = 0.778X + 0.421X + 0.003X + 0.158X + 14.723$ means that when each of resource materials utilization and Economics students' study skills increase by one unit (i.e. 1%), students' respect for cultural and social values skills increases significantly by 77.8% and 42.1% respectively while a unit increase in students perception of teachers' evaluation method and students perception of teachers' attitude insignificantly increased students' respect for cultural and social values skills by 0.3%, and 15.8% respectively.

The result as presented in Table 11 also shows the model summary and overall fit statistics. The Table showed that adjusted R^2 of the model was 0.156 with $R^2 = 0.160$ that indicates that the combined contribution of the variables: Resource utilization, teachers' attitude, students' study skills and teachers' evaluation method accounted for 16.0% of the variation in students' respect for cultural

and social values skills and with the F change value ($F_{(4, 822)} = 13.767$, $p < 0.05$) the combined contribution of the variables is significant.

Research Question 9: What are the relative and composite contributions of curriculum implementation variables (Resource utilization, teachers' attitude, students' study skills and teachers' evaluation method) to students' resources management skills?

Table 12: Beta coefficient and t-ratio for relative and composite contribution of curriculum implementation variables to students' resources management skills

R = 0.467 R ² = 0.218 Adj R ² = 0.214 F _(2, 822) = 57.3	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	43.898	10.327		4.251	.000
Resource Utilization	.049	.303	.005	.163	.870
Students' Perception of Teachers' Attitude	.098	.021	.149	4.788	.000
Students' Perception of Evaluation Methods	.082	.027	.094	3.055	.002
Economics Students' Study Skills	.490	.037	.417	13.378	.000

Table 12 shows that the sign of the coefficient of the independent variables (Resource utilization, teachers' attitude, students' study skills and teachers' evaluation method) were positive. This implies that students' achievement in Economics increased with increase in each of the independent variables. Also, the probability ($p < .05$) as reported in Table 12 for students perception of teachers' attitude, students perception of teachers' evaluation method and Economics students' study skills implies that the slopes ($\beta = 0.098$, $\beta = 0.082$ and $\beta = 0.490$) were statistically significant but Economics resource material utilization with the slope ($\beta = 0.0094$) was statistically not significant. The intercept ($\beta = 43.898$, $p < .05$) as shown in the Table was also significant. Thus regression line $Y = 0.049X + 0.098X + 0.082X + 0.490X + 43.898$ means that when each of students' perception of teachers' attitude, students' perception of teachers' evaluation method and Economics students' study skills increase by one unit (i.e. 1%), students' achievement in Economics increases significantly by 9.8%, 8.2% and 49.0% respectively while a unit increase in resource utilization insignificantly increased students' achievement in Economics by 4.9%.

The result as presented in Table 12 also shows the model summary and overall fit statistics. The Table showed that adjusted R² of the model was 0.214 with R² = 0.218 that indicates that the combined contributions of the variables: Resource utilization, teachers' attitude, students' study skills and teachers' evaluation method accounted for 21.8% of the variation in students' resources management skills and with the F change value ($F_{(4, 822)} = 57.312$, $p < 0.05$) the combined contribution of the variables is significant.

Research Question 10: What are the relative composite contributions of curriculum implementation variables (Resource utilization, teachers’ attitude, students’ study skills and teachers’ evaluation method) to students’ solution to economics problem skills?

Table 13: Beta coefficient and t-ratio for relative and composite contribution of curriculum implementation variables to students’ solution to economic problem skills

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	45.240	11.594		3.902	.000
Resource Utilization	.109	.340	-.010	-.321	.748
Students’ Perception of Teachers’ Attitude	.162	.023	-.213	-7.046	.000
Students’ Perception of Evaluation Methods	.014	.030	.014	.470	.639
Economics Students’ Study Skills	.607	.041	.446	14.766	.000

Table 13 shows that the sign of the coefficient of the independent variables (Resource utilization, teachers’ attitude, students’ study skills and teachers’ evaluation method) were positive. This implies that students’ solution to Economics problem skills increased with increase in each of the independent variables. Also, in Table 13, students’ perception of teachers’ attitude and Economics students’ study skills with the slopes ($\beta = 0.162$ and $\beta = 0.607$) were statistically significant. However, Economics resource material utilization and Students’ Perception of Evaluation Methods with the slopes ($\beta = 0.109$ and $\beta = 0.014$) respectively were statistically not significant. The intercept ($\beta = 45.240$, $p < .05$) as shown in the Table was also significant. Thus regression line $Y = 0.109X + 0.162X + 0.014X + 0.604X + 45.240$ means that when each of students’ perception of teachers’ attitude and Economics students’ study skills increased by one unit (i.e. 1%), students’ achievement in Economics increased significantly by 16.2% and 60.4% respectively while a unit increase in resource utilization and students’ perception of teachers’ evaluation method insignificantly increased students’ solution to Economics problem skills by 10.9% and 1.4% respectively.

The result as presented in Table 13 also shows the model summary and overall fit statistics. The Table showed that adjusted R^2 of the model was 0.262 with $R^2 = 0.266$ that indicates that the combined contributions of the variables: Resource utilization, teachers’ attitude, students’ study skills and teachers’ evaluation method accounted for 26.6% of the variation in students’ solution to Economics problem skills and with the F change value ($F_{(4, 822)} = 74.39$, $p < 0.05$) the combined contribution of the variables is significance.

5.1 Summary of Findings

The research results presented and discussed are summarized as follows:

- The students' performance in Economics achievement test was average.
- The resource utilization correlated highly with the curriculum implementation. This showed that resource utilization influenced Economics achievement. The other four variables were not significant to curriculum implementation. Resource availability, teachers' attitude, students' study skills and teachers' evaluation methods recorded negative relationship because resources were inadequate for teaching of Economics and both the teachers and the students are operating in an environment not conducive to learning.
- There were competent Economics teachers in terms of experience and qualification to handle Economics and, there were more male than female Economics teachers in Oyo state secondary schools.
- Students' perception of teachers' attitude and students' study skills correlated positively with students' respect for dignity of labour skills. Resource utilization and students' study skills correlated positively with students' respect for cultural and social value skills. Students' perception of teachers attitude, students perception of teachers evaluation methods and students study skills correlated positively with students resource management skills
- Students' perception of teachers' attitude to teaching and Economics students' study skills correlated positively with students' solution to Economics problem skills.
- The study skills had negative correlation with students' perception of Economics resource management skills, solution to Economics problem skills, respect for dignity of labour skills and respect for cultural and social value skills. This indicated that Economics knowledge did not assist the students to have skills in: resource management, ability to solve economic problem, respect for dignity of labour and respect for cultural and social value. This is because where the teachers and the students are operating was not conducive for the effective teaching and learning of Economics.

CONCLUSION

The study revealed that there are other Economics objectives apart from achievement in Economics that needs to be seriously addressed such as skills in resource management, respect for dignity of labour, solution to economic problem and respect for cultural social value. This implies that good knowledge of Economics would assist the learners to possess those skills.

RECOMMENDATIONS

It was revealed that, like many good programmers, economics curriculum also suffers setback at the implementation stage. It was therefore recommended that relevant economics textbooks and other economics learning materials should be provided. Students study skill, appreciation of dignity of labour skill ,utilization of economics resources skill to solve economic problems appreciate cultural and social value, economics and teachers attitudes to teaching should be encouraged..Economics teachers should be highly motivated and opportunity for training and retraining programmers should be provided. Their attitudes to teaching of economics in a conducive to learning environment should be made available...

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